

Restoration of forests supports the conservation of pollinators in intensively managed agricultural landscapes

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ABSTRACT

Many intensively managed agricultural landscapes of Europe are extremely poor in forests, which are among fundamental habitats for pollinating insects. To compensate for ongoing forest loss, compensatory afforestation is being widely implemented, especially in deforested areas, although empirical knowledge about its effectiveness for biodiversity conservation is still scarce. Here, we aimed at exploring the potential of biodiversity offsetting through restoration of forests in supporting pollinators in temperate agricultural landscapes. We compared understory pollinator communities between 17 lowland oak-hornbeam restored forest patches older than 20 years with those observed in 17 natural forest remnants, referenced here as the target habitat of ecological restoration. Species richness, abundance, and evenness of bees and hoverflies did not differ between restored and remnant forests, while we observed a lower abundance and higher evenness of lepidopterans in restored forests. The community composition of pollinators between the two forest types was similar. The taxonomic diversity of all pollinator taxa was positively related to canopy openness and flower diversity, while lepidopterans were also found to be sensitive to forest fragmentation at the landscape level. Comparing restored forests with natural reference systems suggested that the restoration of forests has the potential to support pollinators in degraded agricultural landscapes. Our results further provide valuable insights to guide forest ecological restoration targeting pollinators, in view of several ambitious conservation and restoration commitments undertaken at international level.

1. Introduction

Forests are increasingly acknowledged as fundamental habitats for several pollinator taxa (Mola et al., 2021; Tamaru et al., 2023; Ulyshen et al., 2023). Beside floral resources, forests provide pollinators with nesting, reproduction, and overwintering sites, nest-building material, and sheltered habitats (Ulyshen et al., 2023). Ecological research on pollinators has so far largely focused on the effects of forest cover and proximity on the provision of pollination services to adjacent crops (Garibaldi et al., 2011; González-Chaves et al., 2020; Ricketts et al., 2008; Urban-Mead et al., 2023) or on the diversity of pollinators along forest edges (Proesmans et al., 2019; Ren et al., 2023; Vujanović et al., 2023). However, forests host a distinct pollinator community and only

recently more efforts have been made to investigate the diversity of pollinators associated to forest interiors and their features (Allen and Davies, 2023; Milberg et al., 2021; Perlík et al., 2023; Smith et al., 2021; Ulyshen et al., 2024; Viljur et al., 2020).

In Europe, the development of infrastructures and the expansion of remunerative market sectors, e.g. the wine industry, are continuously leading to remarkable land use changes, especially at the expense of forests (Basso, 2019; Brock, 2023; Razaque and Lester, 2021; Troxler and Zabel, 2021). Against ongoing biodiversity losses caused by economic development activities, a frequently adopted international conservation policy is to compensate the loss of natural values with offsetting, i.e. the re-creation of lost habitat elsewhere (Bull and Strange, 2018). Although widely implemented, biodiversity offsetting lacks

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empirical evidence of its efficacy (Josefsson et al., 2021), especially in forest ecosystems (zu Ermgassen et al., 2019). The offset of impacts is legally required in Natura 2000 areas (EU Habitats Directive, 1992) and after forest clearance in some European countries ('compensatory afforestation') (Rega, 2013; Schulz et al., 2023). In Italy, compensation after forest clearance is regulated by National Decree no. 227/2001, but observance of national matters on forests is devolved to the regional level (Rega, 2013). In this context, most of the forest clearance and conversion to other land uses occurs in highly forested landscapes in the pre-Alps (Basso, 2019), while the compensation efforts are concentrated by the regional administrations to the ecological restoration of lowland areas, extremely scarce in forests.

The restoration of forests in human-modified landscapes creates novel habitats, which can be colonised by several forest-dependent species (Filgueiras et al., 2021), including pollinators (Fuller et al., 2018). On the one hand, the diversity and abundance of pollinating insects is affected by the local habitat quality, comprising both foraging and nesting resources, such as floral abundance and plant diversity, and stand structural heterogeneity (Fuller et al., 2018; Penone et al., 2019; Proesmans et al., 2019; Ulyshen et al., 2024). On the other hand, pollinators are affected also by the surrounding landscape composition and configuration, and specialists or less mobile species might suffer from reduced forest cover and connectivity (Brückmann et al., 2010; Ulyshen et al., 2023; Viljur et al., 2022). Despite their size, small forest patches in human-modified landscapes can harbour disproportionately high biodiversity, including insect species of conservation concern and habitat specialist species (Fuller et al., 2018; Proesmans et al., 2019;

Riva and Fahrig, 2022).

In this study, we investigated the effects of forest restoration and forests' local, and landscape characteristics on the diversity and composition of pollinators. Specifically, the objectives of this study were: i) to compare pollinator communities between restored forests and natural forest remnants, the latter referenced here as the target of ecological restoration; and ii) to identify local and landscape factors influencing pollinator diversity in forests. Considering the significant emphasis on biodiversity offsetting as a key tool in international conservation policy, the goal of our study was to contribute to filling the gap of empirical knowledge regarding the effectiveness of regional-level compensatory afforestation in supporting pollinator communities in degraded agricultural landscapes. Our study also aimed at identifying important forest features to consider for optimising conditions for pollinators, in view of several ambitious commitments undertaken by the European Union to restore forests and reverse pollinators decline (European Commission, 2019, 2020).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area and sampling design

This study was conducted in the Po Valley (NE Italy), the largest floodplain in Southern Europe. The study area is dominated by intensive agriculture, with cereals and soybean as the dominant crops, interspersed with urban settlements and semi-natural features, such as hedges and short-rotation poplar plantations. Within this temperate lowland

Fig. 1. Map of the study area and the sampling sites, with inset map in the bottom right showing an example of sampling site with the surrounding land use composition.

area, typical forests are Sub-Atlantic and medio-European oak or oak-hornbeam forests of the *Carpinion betuli* and *Erythronio-Carpinion* (Natura 2000 codes 9160 and 91L0) that have been subjected to severe habitat fragmentation and loss. In fact, such habitat types are considered in an 'unfavourable conservation status' throughout Europe (European Environmental Agency, 2009).

We selected a total of 34 sites: 17 restored forest patches and 17 natural forest remnants (Fig. 1, Fig.S1). Due to the spatial mismatch between originally cleared forests and compensated sites at the regional level, which results in changes in forest type and other environmental factors, we selected natural forest remnants as controls. This choice also allowed to compare the restored sites to a meaningful reference system, i.e. a target restoration outcome. As both restored sites and remnants are extremely rare in the study area, their spatial arrangement did not allow for a paired design. The minimum distance between sites was on average 4.5 km (range: 0.2 km – 12.5 km). We selected reforested sites with a gradient in years since forest plantation (min = 22 years, max = 37 years). Stand age was obtained from records of various forest administrations. Sampled forest patches were either managed as conservation sites or unmanaged. A summary of selected sites' characteristics is provided in Table 1.

2.2. Pollinator sampling

Sites were surveyed three times from the end of April to the end of June 2022. Within each forest site, we conducted a 40-minute transect to sample pollinating insects, namely bees, hoverflies, and lepidopterans, including butterflies and burnet moths. Transects were corridors ca. 5 m wide and were conducted by two surveyors simultaneously (first and second author of this study), walking ca. 2 m apart. We divided each sampling transect into eight sub-units, each of 5 min and with an approximate length of 60 m to estimate rarefaction curves and evaluate sampling coverage (Fig. S2). Along the transects, insects were caught either while flying, or resting on the vegetation, or while visiting flowers. Even if they were not collected while visiting flowers, we assumed that all considered insect groups belonged to the functional group of pollinators. Individuals that could be identified to species level in the field were not collected and were directly recorded. All other specimens were identified to species level later.

2.3. Environmental variables

Within each sampling site, we further estimated the main local forest characteristics. For each sub-transect, we estimated the cover of bare ground, grasses, herbs, and the shrub/tree cover, the latter including woody plants lower than 2 m in height. We further estimated the total flower cover and the cover of each flowering plant species, both as visual estimation of the percentage occupied in the sample area. Next, we

Table 1

Summary statistics of environmental variables (mean \pm SD) estimated in the restored sites and the remnant forests sampled in this study. *P*-values are from a two sample *t*-test. Bold *p*-values indicate significant differences.

Variable	Unit	Restored (N = 17)	Remnant (N = 17)	P value
Canopy cover	%	80.06 \pm 6.64	81.97 \pm 5.13	0.355
Flower cover	%	2.84 \pm 2.42	4.38 \pm 4.59	0.231
Flower species richness	N	9.71 \pm 6.16	10.24 \pm 4.47	0.776
Tree species richness	N	10.76 \pm 4.04	7.76 \pm 2.36	0.014
Tree diameter	cm	20.76 \pm 6.91	35.35 \pm 5.33	<0.001
Patch area	ha	21.77 \pm 33.16	29.07 \pm 48.40	0.612
Connectivity (Si)	–	9.83 \pm 13.68	10.24 \pm 14.14	0.931
Grass cover	%	5.04 \pm 3.89	2.92 \pm 5.08	0.184
Herb cover	%	24.17 \pm 24.83	36.38 \pm 12.92	0.085
Shrub and tree cover	%	43.90 \pm 19.81	31.54 \pm 8.83	0.028
Age	years	25.65 \pm 4.14	–	–

recorded the tree composition of each sub-transect by identifying and visually estimating the percentage basal area of each woody plant species (shrub or tree) higher than 2 m. Moreover, we estimated the canopy cover three times in each sub-transect using the GLAMA app (Tichý, 2016), resulting in 24 estimates per site and per sampling round. For the analyses, vegetation cover estimates were averaged across sub-transects and sampling rounds, resulting in estimates per site. We computed the Shannon diversity of the tree species (H) using *vegan* package (Oksanen et al., 2022). Finally, we visually estimated the mean height and diameter of the dominant tree layer for each site. Visual estimations were performed and agreed by two surveyors (EG and DG) with an education background in forestry.

At the landscape scale, we considered variables related to forest fragmentation, including habitat area and connectivity using the Hanski's connectivity index (Si). Si was calculated by measuring edge-to-edge distances between each study site and all other forest patches in a 10 km radius, using the Eq. (1):

$$Si_i = \sum_{i \neq j} \exp(-\alpha d_{ij}) A_j^b \quad (1)$$

where Si_i is connectivity index of patch i , α is a coefficient of the negative exponential function that determines how the weight given to the surrounding patches decreases with distance and it is related to the dispersal ability (1/average migration distance in km), d_{ij} is distance between patches i and j , A_j is area of patch j , related to emigration by factor b , which scales movement to the size of the surrounding habitat patches (Moilanen and Hanski, 2006). We chose $\alpha=1$, as we expect an average migration distance of 1 km for the studied pollinator groups (Kleijn and van Langevelde, 2006; Krauss et al., 2003; Zurbuchen et al., 2010). For the scaling parameter b we chose $b = 0.3$.

2.4. Statistical analyses

Due to the large number of potential predictors, we first tested only the effect of forest type (i.e. forest remnant versus restored site) on pollinator species richness, abundance, and community evenness using general linear models. We tested each sampled pollinator group (i.e. bees, hoverflies, and lepidopterans) separately, pooling their number of species and abundance observed at site level. Community evenness was calculated using Evar index with the R package *fundiv* (Bartomeus, 2013). To meet the assumption of normally distributed residuals, we used a natural logarithmic transformation of pollinators abundance. We performed the models of bee abundance and evenness both including and excluding honeybees.

Second, we analysed changes in the community composition between forest remnants and restored sites. To visualise the spatial community dissimilarity of species composition, we performed two-dimensional nonmetric multidimensional scaling ordination (NMDS) on presence-absence data. To test for differences in community composition between forest types, we performed permutational multivariate analyses of variance (PERMANOVA) using the function *adonis2*. All analyses were performed separately for bees (including and excluding honeybees), hoverflies, and lepidopterans. We repeated the same analysis excluding rare pollinators, which were defined as those species with an incidence of 5 or less occurrences across all sampling sites.

Third, we investigated the effects of forest features on pollinator diversity in lowland forests using multiple linear regression models. To avoid overfitting of the models due to the large number of potential interactions, we first tested the effect of forest characteristics in interaction with forest type alone. Forest type and tree diameter were highly correlated, so we excluded the latter in the analyses. Since no significant interactions were detected, in the following models we did not include forest type as explanatory variable, i.e. we pooled restored and remnant sites together. We examined the effects of both local variables related to

the composition, structure and heterogeneity of forest stands, and landscape variables related to the dispersal ability of studied insect groups. We used multi-model inference within an information theoretic framework to compare the fit of a set of models rather than selecting one single best model based on p values. Global models included pollinator species richness as response variables and mean flower cover, flowering plant species richness, tree species Shannon diversity (H), mean canopy cover, mean tree diameter, forest patch area, and Hanski connectivity index (Si) as explanatory variables (Fig. S3). Furthermore, in the global models we included interaction terms between connectivity and forest patch area, and between canopy cover and forest patch area. All explanatory variables were scaled to mean 0 and standard deviation 1 to make slopes comparable. To assess possible collinearity between predictors, we estimated variance inflation factors (VIFs). As no VIFs > 2 were detected, we retained all candidate predictors in the global model.

Model selection was performed using a multi-model inference approach based on AICc. Nested models within each global model were ordered based on their second-order AICc, with the best fitting model having lowest AICc, indicating the best trade-off between number of parameters and explanatory power. For each nested model, we calculated the difference between the model AICc and the lowest AICc detected (Δ AIC). We set a cutoff value of Δ AIC = 7 to define a top model set, whereas lower-ranked models were treated as less meaningful (Burnham et al., 2011). Next, we computed the model-averaged partial coefficient for each explanatory variable using all models within the top model set and estimated the 95 % confidence intervals around each model-averaged partial coefficient.

Finally, we explored the effect of restoration age on individual pollinator diversity on the subset of the dataset related to offset sites. All statistical analyses were conducted with the Software R version 4.3.1 (R Core Team, 2023). Multi-model inference analyses were performed with the *MuMIn* package (Bartoń, 2023) and all residual diagnostic was checked using *DHARMA* package (Hartig, 2022). For each model, we tested for spatial correlation in the residuals using Moran's I and we did not find significant spatial autocorrelation.

3. Results

3.1. Pollinator observations and vegetation characteristics

In the sampled forests, we identified a total of 92 plant species flowering at the time of our survey. The average flower cover was low and similar in both remnants and restored sites (Table 1). On the contrary, the average canopy cover was high in both forest types (Table 1). C. 70 % of the sampled insects were recorded while flying or resting on the vegetation, whereas only 30 % when visiting flowers. The estimates of rarefaction curves of pollinator species richness presented similar slopes and did not cross, indicating that our estimates were comparable between the two forest types. However, the extrapolated bee species curves and the partially incomplete sample coverage suggest that some bee species might have been under-sampled in the remnant sites (Fig. S1).

We sampled a total of 893 bees (63 species), 1360 hoverflies (65 species), and 457 lepidopterans (16 species). The honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) was the most abundant bee species (434 individuals), followed by *Bombus pascuorum* (61 individuals). The most common hoverfly and lepidopteran species were, respectively, *Episyrphus balteatus* (860 individuals) and *Amata phegea* (252 individuals). We report the full list of sampled species and their abundances in Table S1.

3.2. Effects of forest type on pollinator diversity

We did not detect significant differences in bee and hoverfly species richness, abundance, and evenness between restored and remnant forest sites (Table 2). Excluding honeybees from the analyses yielded similar results (Table S2). Similarly, lepidopteran species richness did not differ

Table 2

Results of general linear models testing for differences in species richness, abundance, and evenness of the sampled pollinator groups between restored and remnant forest habitats. Bold p-values indicate significant differences.

Response variable	df	F value	P value
Bee richness	1,32	0.6519	0.425
Bee abundance	1,32	0.6187	0.437
Bee evenness	1,32	0.4163	0.523
Hoverfly richness	1,32	0.7903	0.381
Hoverfly abundance	1,32	1.7921	0.190
Hoverfly evenness	1,32	0.8602	0.361
Lepidopteran richness	1,32	0.2911	0.593
Lepidopteran abundance	1,32	4.1667	0.050
Lepidopteran evenness	1,31	7.5215	0.010

between the two habitat types. We only detected significant differences in lepidopteran abundance, which was higher in remnant sites, and in lepidopteran evenness, which was higher in restored sites (Fig. 2, Table 2).

PERMANOVA tests based on presence-absence data of pollinators revealed no significant differences between forest remnants and reforested areas for bees ($R^2 = 0.031$, $p = 0.445$), wild bees only ($R^2 = 0.031$, $p = 0.419$), and hoverflies ($R^2 = 0.040$, $p = 0.101$). We only detected significant but weak differences in the composition of lepidopterans between the two forest types ($R^2 = 0.070$, $p = 0.019$; Fig. S4). When excluding rare pollinator species (those occurring only 5 or less times across all sampled sites, i.e., 49 out of 63 bee species, 48 out of 65 hoverfly species, and 11 out of 16 lepidopteran species) we detected significant but weak differences in the hoverfly community ($R^2 = 0.058$, $p = 0.033$), and no differences in the bee ($R^2 = 0.035$, $p = 0.319$) and lepidopteran communities ($R^2 = 0.068$, $p = 0.053$) between the two habitat types.

3.3. Effects of environmental variables on pollinator diversity

Models testing the effect of forest local and landscape characteristics in interaction with forest type did not reveal significant interactions for any groups (Table S3, Table S4, Table S5). To avoid overfitting, we therefore present here only models with no interactions with forest type (i.e., remnants + restored sites, $N = 34$).

For bee species richness as response variable, multi-model inference identified 96 models constituting the top model set with a Δ AIC < 7 (Table S6). Our averaged model showed that bee species richness was significantly related to flower cover and forest canopy cover (Table 3). In particular, increasing flower cover and decreasing forest canopy cover had a positive effect on the species richness of bees (Fig. 3a,

Fig. 2. Predicted values of lepidopteran abundance (a) and evenness (b) between restored and remnant sites. Error bars are 95 % confidence intervals. Lepidopteran evenness was calculated using Evar index.

Table 3

Model-averaged conditional results obtained after multi-model inference analysis on bee, hoverfly, and lepidopteran species richness. Si = Hanski's connectivity index; Tree H = Tree Shannon diversity. Bold p-values indicate significant differences.

	Estimate	SE	Adjusted SE	z value	P value
a) Bee					
(Intercept)	8.278	0.606	0.632	13.105	<0.001
Flower cover	1.615	0.707	0.736	2.194	0.028
Canopy cover	-1.923	0.790	0.818	2.352	0.019
Area	-1.113	0.689	0.716	1.554	0.120
Flower richness	1.638	0.917	0.946	1.731	0.084
Connectivity (Si)	0.742	0.776	0.807	0.920	0.358
Tree Shannon diversity	0.671	0.653	0.681	0.986	0.324
Tree diameter	-0.642	0.724	0.751	0.854	0.393
Canopy cover * Area	1.376	1.001	1.038	1.325	0.185
Area * Connectivity (Si)	-1.058	2.514	2.589	0.408	0.683
b) Hoverfly					
(Intercept)	8.764	0.437	0.455	19.232	<0.001
Canopy cover	-2.596	0.506	0.525	4.938	< 0.001
Tree Shannon diversity	0.971	0.460	0.47	2.025	0.042
Connectivity (Si)	-0.523	0.505	0.526	0.993	0.320
Area	0.380	0.458	0.478	0.795	0.426
Tree diameter	0.263	0.516	0.535	0.491	0.623
Flower richness	0.411	0.555	0.578	0.712	0.476
Flower cover	-0.022	0.490	0.510	0.045	0.964
Canopy cover * Area	-0.045	0.601	0.627	0.073	0.941
Area * Connectivity (Si)	-0.454	1.104	1.154	0.393	0.694
c) Lepidopteran					
(Intercept)	2.795	0.241	0.251	11.098	<0.001
Area	-0.448	0.255	0.266	1.684	0.092
Flower richness	0.729	0.301	0.313	2.33	0.019
Connectivity (Si)	0.701	0.278	0.289	2.422	0.015
Flower cover	-0.395	0.284	0.296	1.335	0.182
Tree diameter	0.233	0.266	0.277	0.839	0.401
Canopy cover	0.083	0.342	0.354	0.236	0.813
Tree Shannon diversity	-0.123	0.261	0.272	0.451	0.652
Area * Connectivity (Si)	0.139	0.626	0.653	0.213	0.831
Canopy cover * Area	0.362	0.373	0.388	0.934	0.350

Fig. 3b).

For hoverfly species richness as response variable, 40 models showed $\Delta AIC < 7$ (Table S7). Top model averaging indicated that canopy cover and tree diversity significantly affected hoverfly species richness in forests (Table 3). In particular, hoverfly species richness increased with increasing diversity of tree species in the forest, while it decreased with increasing canopy cover (Fig. 3c, Fig. 3d).

For lepidopteran species richness as response variable, we identified 55 models with $\Delta AIC < 7$ (Table S8). Top model averaging indicated that increasing flower richness and connectivity positively affected butterfly species richness in forest habitats (Fig. 3e, Fig. 3f, Table 3). The hypothesized interactions between site area and connectivity with other forest patches and between site area and canopy cover did not affect the richness of neither bee, nor hoverfly, nor lepidopteran species (Table 3).

Only for restored sites, we also tested the effect of forest age. The latter was not significant for any of the studied groups (Table S9).

4. Discussion

Our study assessed the potential of compensatory afforestation carried out at regional level to support the conservation of forest-associated pollinator communities. Restored and natural remnant forests, as target habitats of restoration, presented very similar pollinator communities, suggesting that the restoration of forests in degraded landscapes has the potential to create suitable conditions for pollinators. Most of the pollinators responded positively to open forest conditions, while lepidopterans benefitted also from forest connectivity at the landscape scale.

Fig. 3. Predictions and 95 % confidence intervals for the effect of (a) flower cover and (b) canopy cover on bee species richness, (c) canopy cover and (d) tree diversity (Shannon index) on hoverfly species richness, (e) flower richness and (f) connectivity (Hanski's index) on lepidopteran species richness. Predictions are from the best model in each candidate set. Model-averaged estimates are listed in Table 3.

4.1. Effects of forest type on pollinator diversity

Our results indicate that restored forests hosted similar bee and hoverfly communities compared to natural forest remnants. On the contrary, we found that lepidopteran communities in natural forests slightly differed in abundance, evenness, and composition compared to those in restored sites. Natural forest remnants were characterised by higher lepidopteran abundances of species associated with woodland habitats, such as *Amata phegea*, while restored sites hosted fewer individuals, but included additional species linked to open habitats, such as *Pieris* spp., thus explaining the observed differences in evenness patterns. Such differences are likely caused by species-specific requirements and are expected to reduce as the restored sites evolve towards greater woodland maturity conditions over time.

Our results suggest that forest restoration in deforested agricultural landscapes has the potential to support pollinator communities in the same way natural forest remnants do. While it is well established that restoring habitats benefits the conservation of bees and hoverflies compared to unrestored, degraded habitats (Fuller et al., 2018; Tonietto and Larkin, 2018; Ulrich and Sargent, 2025), no research had, to our knowledge, previously evaluated the effectiveness of forest restoration in comparison with reference temperate forest systems and targeting forest-associated pollinators. Our results are promising and contrast with similar studies evaluating other restored ecosystems compared to

their natural references. For instance, although α -diversity was similar, prairie restorations did not fully restore the composition and spatial variability of bee communities typical of well-preserved, protected remnants, potentially due to differences in the floral community (Lane et al., 2022). Similarly, neither quarry active restoration nor spontaneous succession converged to similar natural reference pollinator communities (Carvalho et al., 2022).

4.2. Effects of local habitat quality

At the local scale, the diversity of both bees and hoverflies was linked to low canopy cover, suggesting that light is a major abiotic driver of pollinator biodiversity in forests. High canopy cover reduced the diversity of pollinators probably due to less solar radiation reaching the understory and influencing both air temperature and the development of a flower-rich forest floor (Della Longa et al., 2020), with cascading effects on photophilic species such as pollinators (Davies et al., 2023). Some studies further suggest that open conditions in less dense forests increase flower display and its attractiveness to pollinators (Coulin et al., 2019). Our results are consistent with other studies exploring the response of several aboveground arthropods and finding the same pattern across a variety of forest ecosystems (Davies et al., 2023; Davis and Comai, 2022; Eckerter et al., 2022; Penone et al., 2019; Piccini et al., 2024; Ulyshen et al., 2024).

Furthermore, we found that the studied pollinator taxa responded differently to other local forest conditions. There are key functional and ecological differences between bees, hoverflies, and lepidopterans, which could explain these patterns. In our study, hoverfly species richness was found to be sensitive to the diversity of tree species. Similar patterns were previously reported for hoverflies and bees (Larrieu et al., 2015; Traylor et al., 2024). Earlier research linked the richness of tree species to a greater variation in tree diameter, which was found to positively affect forest-associated hoverflies (Fuller et al., 2018). Almost all of the hoverfly species sampled in the present study are strictly associated with deciduous forest environments (Speight, 2017). The diversity of trees and other woody plants may have favoured both saproxylic species strongly relying on microhabitats - such as tree holes - for breeding and larval feeding (Vujić et al., 2023) and species whose larvae feed on tree aphids. Moreover, some flowering trees and shrubs commonly found in oak-hornbeam forests, such as *Crataegus* sp., *Acer* sp., *Tilia* sp., and *Prunus* sp., can provide nutritious pollen and nectar for adults, thus attracting a higher diversity of pollinator species (Allen and Davies, 2023; Ulyshen et al., 2023; Wood et al., 2022).

Similarly, bee species richness was found to respond positively to foraging resources, such as the flower cover in the understory layer. Flowers are typically scarce in the herb layer of closed-canopy forests, forcing bees to search for nectar in neighbouring open habitats or in the canopy. However, spring-blooming of herbaceous plants in broadleaved temperate forest systems can provide an early and abundant foraging resource prior to canopy closure and to advancing growing season (Ulyshen et al., 2023), thus retaining many pollinator species to the forest interiors. Local flowering plant species richness was shown to positively affect lepidopteran diversity, which rely on different plant species for their larval development (Dennis et al., 2006). A positive correlation between local host plant diversity and butterflies has been extensively documented also in other ecosystems (Hawkins and Porter, 2003; Krämer et al., 2012).

4.3. Effects of patch size and connectivity

Across the dominant agricultural matrix of our study area, bees and hoverflies sampled in forests were not influenced by forest patch size nor by connectivity. Pollinator movement decisions between fragmented habitat patches are thought to be dependent on optimal foraging, so that small, unconnected patches are often avoided (Hadley and Betts, 2012). However, although forest-associated pollinators in an intensive

agricultural landscape may be organized as meta-populations, pollinator movement may not occur solely to structurally defined forest patches. For generalist species, such as most of the species sampled in this study, forests represent potential nesting sites, rather than profitable foraging habitats. In many cases, the agricultural matrix provides a permeable habitat for forest-associated pollinators, which may forage on the rich forest edges (Proesmans et al., 2019; Schlegel, 2022), on open habitats (Moquet et al., 2018) or on the interspersed semi-natural habitats in the landscape (Schirmel et al., 2018). The agricultural land in our study area probably imposed no barrier to movements, and pollinators could move freely across different habitats. Scientific evidence in this regards is mixed, as a number of studies have found negative effects of patch isolation on hoverfly species richness (Herrault et al., 2016; Ouin et al., 2006), while other have found no significant relationships due to either high species mobility or the relative importance of local variables (Fuller et al., 2018).

On the contrary, we found a negative effect of habitat isolation on butterflies. This finding concurs with several studies across multiple habitats showing the negative influence of reduced landscape connectivity on lepidopterans and plant specialists (Brückmann et al., 2010; Öckinger et al., 2012; Thomas et al., 2001; Viljur et al., 2022). While it is true that most butterflies use several habitat types to find supplementary or complementary resources, evidence highlights the paramount importance of forest land at large spatial scales, likely related to the colonisation-extinction balance in a meta-population context (Bergman et al., 2018; Luppi et al., 2018; Tammaru et al., 2023; Viljur et al., 2020). Forest cover in the landscape matrix is regarded as an even more important variable than grassland fragmentation also for the richness of grassland specialists (Öckinger et al., 2012). Thus, even for non-forest butterfly specialists, increasing the matrix quality with forest restoration and re-creation and improving its edges with surrounding farmland are thought to be key conservation strategies, irrespective of adjacent land use intensity (Öckinger et al., 2012; Schlegel, 2022).

4.4. Study limitations

There are two main limitations in our study. First, pollinator sampling has been performed only at the ground level, despite the potential for the canopy to harbour foraging pollinators (Allen and Davies, 2023; Ulyshen et al., 2010). While canopy cover and subsequent light conditions in the understory has emerged as one of the most important variables affecting bee and hoverfly diversity in forests, the upper canopy receives sunlight throughout the season and potentially represents a stable, favourable habitat for bees (Allen and Davies, 2023) and hoverflies (Birtele and Hardersen, 2012). Despite the logistic challenge, future research should aim at integrating understory with overstory sampling, to provide a complete picture on pollinator diversity in forests. Second, due to the very limited number of natural forest remnants in our study region, we could not select highly preserved patches. In fact, there is evidence of a widespread degradation of temperate forests in the lowlands of Northern Italy (Gaglio et al., 2023; Vacchiano et al., 2016). The observed lack of differences with reforested sites may also indicate a low conservation status of the natural remnant forests, with the loss of typical and specialist pollinator species. We did sample a few hoverfly species typical of mature and overmature mesophilic oak-hornbeam forests (e.g. *Criorhina berberina*, *Caliprobola speciosa*, *Eupeodes nitens*) but these were not sufficient in driving a significant difference with restored habitats, because their incidence across forest remnants was rather limited. Our study advocates for the need for pollinator species reference databases, against which to assess the conservation status of ecosystems, such as primary lowland oak-hornbeam forests. An example of such reference database exists for hoverflies (*Syrph the Net*) (Speight, 2017) and it has been widely applied to assess the conservation status of remnant forests (Maritano, 2020), the quality of agroecosystems (Burgio and Sommaggio, 2007) or in other ecological studies (Moquet et al., 2018).

5. Conclusions

The current conservation policy of restoring forests in deforested agricultural landscapes to compensate for the loss of stands in forest-dominated landscapes appears as an effective strategy to support pollinators in degraded landscapes. However, due to the spatial mismatch between cleared forests and restored forests, it is important to notice that the biodiversity offsetting approach evaluated in this study does not directly compensate for the forest clearance and the associated loss of biodiversity. Instead, the restoration of lowland forests benefits pollinators communities relying on the foraging and nesting resources present in the few forested patches within a degraded agricultural matrix. Despite the impact of forest clearance not directly compensated for, we show that compensatory afforestation at regional level can enhance the quality of intensive agricultural landscapes, thus promoting the conservation of forest-associated pollinator communities inhabiting them. This study presents encouraging results, considering the emphasis on biodiversity offsetting as a key instrument in international conservation policy. However, extensive deforestation and landscape degradation are likely to reduce the effectiveness of conservation programs aimed at recovering biodiversity and the services they provide. Specific strategies, such as increasing canopy openness, enhancing flowering plant diversity, and prioritising connectivity among forest patches are likely to maximise restoration efforts for pollinators and other species of conservation concern. Even though our study did not highlight strong differences in pollinator communities between restored forests and natural forest remnants, biodiversity offsetting should be implemented with care, prioritising the conservation of natural forests remnants.

Open research statement

The data are available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778588>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Elena Gazzea: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Davide Gobbo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Maurizio Mei:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Dino Paniccia:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Giacomo Trotta:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Francesco Boscutti:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Lorenzo Marini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111008>.

Data availability

The data are available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778588>.

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